

Factor Analysis of Teachers' Attitudes Towards Partnership with Parents

Nejra Krnić¹, Elma Selmanagić – Lizde²

¹ Elementary School "Richmond Park International Primary School", Sarajevo

² University of Sarajevo – Faculty of Educational Sciences

Abstract

The interaction between family and school is of utmost importance for recognizing the specific factors in the educational process. The key factors related to the development of partnerships between the family and the school are the interaction of teachers with parents, the participation of the family in school activities and the educational process and creating an environment which will encourage parents to be more open for giving back feedbacks. The aim of this study is to examine the factors which strengthen family – school partnership. The study involved 164 elementary school teachers and the research was conducted in Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Data collection was done through a questionnaire consisting of 17 statements, designed specifically for the purposes of the study. Factor analysis of the attitudes of teachers towards partnership with parents is based on the processing of the results obtained by survey collection of opinions and attitudes. The study resulted in the extraction of four factors. The factors that teachers consider to contribute to strengthening partnerships are providing parental support, transparency of school work, active encouragement of parents and providing support for child development.

Article history

Received: 30.5.2025.

Accepted: 17.6.2025.

Keywords:

Partnership;
Teachers;
School;
Parents.

¹ Corresponding author's email: hadzienejra@gmail.com

Introduction

The primary goal of the family-school partnership is to create long-lasting effects on the development of the child and to create consistency between school and family. In this process, families can be involved in the educational process of the child in different ways, but with the help and initiative of the school. One of the goals of teachers is to provide positive relationships and a reliable environment in which parents will feel free to engage in the educational process. To achieve this and to maintain a high level of parental involvement, it is necessary for teachers to adjust the style of partnership that will be accepted by parents. The partnership puts the child and his/her well-being in the center of attention both by the school and by parents who have the same interests, goals and tasks (Ljubetić, 2014). National standards for family-to-school partnerships are based on the theoretical and empirical work of Epstein (Epstein et al. 2019). School, family and community are seen as three overlapping spheres that should work together for the benefit of the child. This shows that normative and scientific discourse are intertwined. Empirical research has shown that there are several characteristics related to the high quality of the relationship between family and school and they include: the degree of teacher education, working experience, teacher training and professional development (Knoche, et al. 2009). The values and expectations of teachers, including prejudices, stereotypes or expectations they have from the family, combined with the self-efficacy of teachers, can be an obstacle in relationships with families. According to Heatly, Votruba – Drzal (2017), when teachers have negative experiences with families, it can form negative stereotypes and their implications and it can lead to reduced efforts of teachers to engage families in the classroom, which therefore affects the involvement of parents in school. Such attitudes have a detrimental effect on the teacher – child interaction in the classroom, which leads to negative perceptions and conflicts between the teacher and the child. Teacher education, training and professional development provide the potential to increase awareness and understanding of issues related to cultural differences and contextual factors affecting parental inclusion (Miller, 2016). Also, King et al. (2003) found that teacher training related to family practices provides an improvement in attitudes about the family. The teacher's duties could also be summarized as follows: the teacher should have a very good knowledge of the family inclusion program, should respond clearly and concisely to family questions, establish open communication with parents, monitor that families fully and properly implement the set participation program, regularly take notes of children, prepare and implement programs according to the needs of families and children, assess the program they implement once a month through evaluation forms sent to families (Carlisle et.al.2005). To develop an effective partnership, teachers need to possess professional and personal competences. Professional competences include the ability for teachers to identify the needs of students for learning, giving parents adequate instructions, as well as organizing activities based on didactic and pedagogical knowledge. Didactic competencies are defined as having knowledge of the learning process, monitoring individual differences of students, adapting communication using modern teaching strategies and evaluating all dimensions of teaching work (Selmanagić -Lizde, Sarić, 2024). Personal competencies are related to a positive attitude towards students, the ability to establish positive relationships with parents, and the passion for teaching. According to Selmanagić - Lizde, Sarić (2024) personal competencies also consider emotional intelligence, motivation, professional development, reflection and relationship with students and their parents. Parent involvement means involving family members in educational programs to support children through the educational process. The concept of parental involvement is often known as the participation of parents in classroom activities as well as frequent communication and cooperation with the school and teacher

(Morrison, 2013) Parental involvement in education includes behaviours such as: taking care of students and their tasks, communicating with school, cooperating, monitoring children's grades and attendance, being aware of the learning deficiencies of their children and striving to correct them (Epstein, 2002). Parental involvement can also be defined as an interest in children's educational life, regular communication with children's teachers and observation of children's behavior at home and at school. It also states that the involvement of parents refers to the connection between parents and teachers, the support of children's educational life and parental rules with consequences on school life (Knisely, 2011). Beside the term parent involvement, we will also consider the concept of parental engagement. Bettencourt et.al. (2023) state that different terms have been used to define the concept of parental engagement, such as parental participation, parental involvement, family engagement. Therefore, they state that they use the term parental engagement for two reasons. One of the reason is that they believe that school engagement is mainly focused on strengthening relationships with parents, and the second reason is that most research linking parental engagement to children's academic success has been obtained from one family member.

Based on the above mentioned facts, the aim of the research is to examine teachers perception regarding partnership with parents and to determine the factors which strengthen the family – school partnership. Based on the results obtained, we will develop guidelines for strengthening family – school partnership.

Method

Sample

The research was conducted on a sample of 164 elementary school teachers (160 or 97.6% females and 4 or 2.4% males) from Federation Bosnia and Herzegovina. Most respondents have 5-15 experience in education (45.7%), and the least respondents have 15-25 experience (11%). More than a half of the respondents (56.1%) stated that they have a fourth level of education or VSS, there are 42.1% of masters of science and, as expected, the smallest number of respondents have a secondary education (1.8%).

Instruments

Survey and scaling procedures have been applied as well as appropriate assessment scale instruments. A conveniently prepared survey was created for the needs of this study. Besides basic demographic information (gender, age, school), we examined teachers perceptions towards family – school partnership. The scale is of the Likert type, with ratings from one to five: 1 – Never, 2 – Rarely, 3 – Sometimes, 4 – Often, 5 – Always. The questionnaire consists of 17 statements. Statistical analysis included significant results obtained by factor analysis.

Procedures

The theoretical part of the research was conducted by analyzing the available literature and presenting the previous research. The empirical part of the research was conducted in the period from September to November 2024. The survey was distributed in electronic form. Quantitative methodology was applied for the analysis of data collected through online questionnaires – *Google Forms*, for which we shared the link with class teachers, and the anonymity of participants was ensured. Before the beginning of the research, the participants were explained the goals and purpose of the research and the collected data were used

exclusively for scientific purposes and in accordance with ethical principles of the research. The quantitative data was examined using SPSS software.

Results

In order to better understand the interpretation of data, we will explain what is a multivariate method of factor analysis. Factor analysis directly measure the variables on a representative sample and finds a smaller number of hidden, latent variables. Factor scale analysis for teachers was conducted on 17 particles and four factors were extracted.

Before applying factor analysis, it is necessary to examine whether the preconditions for its use are met. Factor model is based on the assumption that the variables are interconnected. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test is another indicator of the suitability of data for factor analysis. The KMO value is calculated on the basis of correlations between variables and ranges from 0 to 1. Values closer to 1 indicate stronger correlations and greater suitability for factor analysis. The value of the Kaiser – Meyer – Olkin test for our research is 0.808. Since the test limit is 0.60, we conclude that it is an adequate sample for this type of analysis. In order to assess the overall significance of the correlation matrix, the Bartlett test is used. Bartlett test value for the statistical significance of the correlation matrix $\chi^2 = 931,733$ at 136 degrees of freedom and $p < 0,000$ also confirms the suitability of statistical processing of collected data by factor analysis.

This is followed by an analysis of the main components. Using Main Component Analysis will determine the number of factors to be retained. A table called *Total Variance Explained* shows the results of the *Principal Component Analysis (PCA)*. PCA is a statistical method used to reduce the dimensionality of a dataset, aiming to preserve as much of the variability as possible. The four components have eigenvalues greater than 1, and we will keep them accordingly and further analyze them. Their values are shown in Table 2.

Table 1. *Kaiser - Meyer Olkin and Bartlett's Test*

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Advice.		0,808
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	931,733
	Df	136
	Sig.	0,000

Table 2. *Principal Component Analysis*

Component	Eigenvalues		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5,077	29,862	29,862
2	2,215	13,029	42,891
3	1,334	7,849	50,741
4	1,166	6,859	57,599
5	0,959	5,644	63,243
6	0,864	5,083	68,326
7	0,789	4,639	72,966
8	0,688	4,045	77,011
9	0,676	3,975	80,986
10	0,613	3,609	84,594

According to the Kaiser criterion, we are only interested in components whose characteristic value is 1 or more. From the table we can observe four factors that have characteristic values of 1 or more. The characteristic root of the first factor is 5.07, the second 2.21, the third 1.33, and the fourth 1.16. These four components explain a total of 57.59% of variance and explain more than half of the variance of the data, which is a good percentage for analysis. To know which components (factors) are involved, we will use the component matrix.

Factor analysis with Varimax – rotation extracted factors and used the criterion of characteristic root over 1 to obtain the factor (Table 3). The data obtained by the factor analysis show us that the instrument made for the purpose of this research has good metric characteristics. The percentage of total variance is high - 57.59%.

Table 3. *Rotated Component Matrix*

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Relationships	0,730	0,157	0,031	0,073
Volunteering	0,652	0,403	0,290	0,156
Help	0,594	-0,028	0,524	0,077
Survey	0,584	0,058	0,454	0,046
Meeting	0,260	0,656	0,025	0,129
Ideas	0,483	0,617	0,192	0,077
Information	0,232	0,610	0,037	0,035
Days	0,059	0,606	0,196	0,003
Plan	0,508	0,585	-0,021	0,237
Proposal	0,240	0,579	-0,260	0,387
Events	0,080	-0,034	0,788	0,058
Collaboration	0,057	0,125	0,784	0,115
Excursions	0,252	0,204	0,528	-0,083
Presence	- 0,160	0,285	0,156	0,762
Support	0,162	0,108	-0,091	0,718
Communication	0,472	-0,173	0,312	0,532
Programs	0,289	0,056	0,433	0,466
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. ^a				
a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.				

Factor 1 - „Parental involvement through support and volunteering“ includes four variables: relationships, volunteering, help and survey. The full statements for each variable are shown below.

This factor includes the following four statements:

- I have a good relationship with the parents of the students;
- I give parents the opportunity to volunteer (before, during or after the lessons);
- I am available to provide additional assistance in working with children;
- I regularly survey parents with the aim of getting feedback on the degree of satisfaction with the work of the school and partnership with teachers.

Factor 2 „Transparency of school work“ includes six variables: meeting, ideas, information, days, plan, proposal. The full statements are shown below:

- Parents have the possibility to arrange a meeting with me and/or the school management;
- Parents are free to present their ideas and suggestions regarding the work of the school;
- I regularly inform parents about the student and his progress;
- Organize special days for the presentation and promotion of children's academic, sports and artistic achievements;
- I regularly provide opportunities for parents to familiarize themselves with the curriculum;
- Allow parents the opportunity to create suggestions about the work of the school

Factor 3 „Active parent encouragement“ includes the following three variables: events, collaboration, excursions. The full statements are shown below:

- I accept the suggestions and ideas of parents when organizing various school events;
- I am open for cooperation;
- I actively encourage the cooperation with parents when planning and organizing excursions, bazaars or similar events.

Factor 4 „Child development support“ includes four variables: presence, support, communications and programs. The full statements are shown below:

- Provide parents with information on the time and manner in which they can attend certain class activities or school events;
- I provide parents with support in the context of child education;
- Communication with parents contributes to a better understanding of the needs of the child;
- Allow parents to get involved in organizing and improving school programs.

Discussion

The study was conducted to determine factors which strengthen family – school partnership. The results extracted four factors which are important to develop in order to strengthen family -school partnership.

The first factor would consider providing systematic support and creating opportunities for parents to enable parents to participate more actively in the educational process through volunteering and providing regular feedback. Previous statements imply the openness and availability of teachers to work with parents, regular interviewing and receiving feedback from parents, as well as providing additional assistance, all with the aim of a comprehensive approach to involving parents in the educational process. Boonk et. al. (2018) highlighted that various researches have proven that parents' activities such as communication about different children's school activities, checking and helping with homework, and parents' participation in school activities, are considered as the most influential ways of parental involvement. As stated by Deeba et.al. (2021) teachers believe that when they are in contact with parents, they notice the progress of students. They also emphasize that there should be an open discussion between parents during parent-teacher meetings, which could help teachers get feedback from parents.

Erdener, Knoepfel (2018) point out that parents view their involvement in school activities as a key factor that has a major impact on children's education, but they believe that schools should still have the main responsibility for children's education. The second factor relates to the transparency of school work as well as regular and active information for parents. Statements that include this factor relate to the importance of regularly informing parents about the educational achievements of students and the educational process itself, such as the progress of students, but also introducing parents to the curriculum. Also, this factor refers to the possibility of giving parents the opportunity to propose their ideas regarding the work of the school. The positive impact on the relationship between parents and teachers is found in the research by Paccaud et. al. (2021). The results of these studies emphasized that the importance of the relationship between parents and teachers was influenced by the teachers' high personal commitment, respectable relationship with parents and clear discussions. Diverse parental academic involvement involves conversations with teachers about children's academic progress and research results have confirmed that parental academic involvement has a positive effect on student outcomes (Xiong et. al., 2021). Involvement in the form of helping with homework has a positive effect on the success of students in elementary school but this is not the case when it comes to students of subject classes (Wei et.al., 2022). According to Witte, et. al. (2021) the partnership between family and school leads to several important outcomes for children, such as increased academic engagement, completion of homework, fluent reading, success in mathematics and overall academic success, which would not be possible if there is not sufficient parental involvement in the child's educational process.

Variables belonging to third factor focus on the openness of schools and teachers to accept proposals from parents, as well as their active engagement to participate in the planning and organization of events such as bazaars or excursions. This factor aims to strengthen the partnership with parents in organizing different activities at school, all of which leads to an increase in parental engagement at school. Falcon et.al. (2023) highlighted in his research that teachers who consider that the level of their participation is high, state that there is greater family participation in decision -making at school, in contrast to other teachers who consider their level of participation to be low or medium. In our research variables belonging to the last factor relate to providing information on how parents participate in school activities, their support in the education of students, as well as providing opportunities for parents to improve the school's work program. The focus of this factor is to provide access to parents to get more involved in their child's educational process and thus contribute to their overall development. The results indicated the importance of including parents in different school activities, providing them support to be more involved and accepting their opinions regarding school policies and curriculum. Paccaud et.al. (2021) also reported that positive aspects were high teacher commitment, frequent feedback and the flow of information between teachers and parents, the willingness of teachers to take into account the specific needs of the child, as well as the possibility of influencing the decisions made at school.

Successful partnership between family and school requires open and two-way communication, and the school and a competent teacher are important participants in developing that partnership. One of the five areas of teacher competence is teacher competence in the area of educational partnership with parents, as well as competence in the area of organization and management of the educational process. Therefore, the teacher's competence for developing a partnership relationship includes the ability to actively listen, create an open and supportive environment, recognize the effort and work of parents with children, as well as regularly inform parents about the children's progress (Zrilić, Marin,2019). Parental involvement is much more

than just attending parent meetings at school. The creation of an educational environment that requires an effective partnership with the school should be aimed at overcoming the gap between school and home. Based on the results we can give few recommendations for strengthening family – school partnership. The following recommendations can represent a kind of a roadmap on the way to developing and strengthening partnership relations between family and school:

- Open communication between parents and teachers.
- Transparency of school work - creating an environment in which parents will be free to present their ideas, as well as ensuring opportunities for parents to familiarize themselves with the curriculum.
- Active participation of parents - the teacher's task would be to invite parents to become more actively involved in the work of the school.
- Strengthening pedagogical competences - working on developing the pedagogical competencies of teachers is one of the concrete segments of work on developing partnership relationships, which can be done through teacher training.

Study limitations

There are several limitations in this study. The results of the survey were conducted only in the territory of the Federation of BiH, with the largest number of respondents from Sarajevo due to their greater accessibility. The sample consisted of a larger number of female participants. In terms of methodological limitations, quantitative research methods provide the opportunity to collect data from a larger number of respondents and for a deeper insight into the research problem itself, qualitative methods can be used. With a similar setting, but using qualitative methods, it is recommended to conduct research that will reveal the meaning of the family-school partnership in a broader framework.

Conclusions

The results of our research indicated that the factors that strengthen the partnership between family and school are: providing support for teachers through volunteering, transparency of school work, active encouragement of parents and providing support for child development. Based on the presented research results, it is concluded that it is very important that teachers and parents have continuous communication, provide support and exchange ideas, in order to contribute to a positive impact for all participants in education. These factors indicate the need for teachers to create opportunities for parents to be more involved in education through volunteering, making flexible schedule so that most of the parents can participate in various school activities. Furthermore, sharing information and providing various trainings for parents to improve their pedagogical competences and including parents in creating curriculum can lead to successful partnership. The quality of such a partnership leads to an increase in positive outcomes for the student. Teachers and parents have mutual expectations about the process itself and if they fail to meet these expectations it can lead to dissatisfaction and a decrease in the involvement of parents in the educational process. Further studies can include researching the impact of these factors on students achievement.

References

- Bettencourt, A.M., Gross, D., Bower, K., Francis, L., Taylor, K., Singleton, D.L., Han, R.H. (2023). Identifying Meaningful Indicators of Parent Engagement in Early Learning for Low – Income, Urban families. *Urban Education*, Vol. 58, No. 10, 2308–2345
- Boonk, L., Hieronymus, J.M., Henk, R. and Saskia, R.G. (2018). A Review of the Relationship between Parental Involvement Indicators and Academic Achievement. *Educational Research Review*, Vol. 24, 10-30.
- Carlisle, E., Stanley, L., and Kemple, K.M. (2005). Opening Doors : Understanding School and Family Influences On Family Involvement. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 33(3), 155-162.
- Deeba, F., Kahn, H.K., Saleem, A. (2021). Family School Partnership: A Cohesive Perception of Teachers and Parents. *Pakistan Social Sciences Review* April-June 2021, Vol. 5, No. 2, pp. 431-445.
- Epstein, J. (2002). School, Family and Community Partnerships. *Thousand Oaks*, California: Corwin Press.
- Epstein, J. L., Sanders, M. G., Sheldon, S. B., Simon, B. S., Salinas, K. C., Jansorn, N. R., et al. (2019). School, Family, and Community Partnerships. Your Handbook for Action (4. Aufl.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin.
- Erdener, M.A., Knoeppel, R.C. (2018). Parents' perceptions of their involvement in schooling. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science (IJRES)*, Vol. 4, No. 1, 1-13.
- Falcon, J.A.A., Quintana, J.C.M., Sanchez, J.A.A., Pinero, M.A.C. (2023). Teacher Perception About the Families' Participation at School – Factors Predicting Participation. *Educacao and Sociedade*, Vol. 44.
- Heatly, M. C., Votruba-Drzal, E. (2017). Parent-and teacher-child relationships and engagement at school entry: Mediating, interactive, and transactional associations across contexts. *Developmental psychology*, 53(6), 1042.
- King, G., Kertoy, M., King, S., Law, M., Rosenbaum, P., Hurley, P. (2003). A measure of parents' and service providers' beliefs about participation in family-centered services. *Children's Health Care*, 32 (3), 191-214.
- Knisely, K. (2011). Literature review: How much does parental involvement really affect the student's success?
- Knoche, L. L., Sheridan, S. M., Edwards, C. P., Osborn, A. Q. (2010). Implementation of a relationship-based school readiness intervention: A multidimensional approach to fidelity measurement for early childhood. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 25(3), 299- 313.
- Miller, H., Robinson, M., Valentine, J. L., Fish, R. (2016). Is the feeling mutual? Examining parent-teacher relationships in low-income, predominantly Latino schools. *American Journal of Education*, 123 (1), 37-67.
- Morrison, G. (2013). Fundamentals of Early Childhood Education. *Hoboken: Pearson*.
- Paccaud, A., Keller, R., Luder, R., Pastore, G., Kunz, A. (2021). Satisfaction With the Collaboration Between Families and Schools – The Parent's View. *Special Education Needs*. Vol.2021.
- Selmanagić – Lizde, E., Sarić, R. (2024). Pedagoške kompetencije, škola i obitelj. *Sarajevo Publishing*. Sarajevo.
- Ljubetić, M. (2014). Od suradnje do partnerstva obitelji, odgojno-obrazovne ustanove i zajednice. Zagreb: Element.

- Wei, J., Pomerantz, E.M., Ng, F.F.Y., Yu, Y.H., Wang, M.Z. and Wang, Q. (2022). Do the Effects of Parents' Involvement in Youth's Academic Adjustment Vary with Youth's Developmental Phase? A Longitudinal Investigation in China. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, Vol. 71.
- Witte, A.L., Schumacher, R.E., Napoli, A.R. (2021). Family – School Partnership in Elementary School – Working together for kids. *Nebraska Extension, NebGuide*.
- Xiong, Y., Qin, X., Wang, Q., et al. (2021). Parental Involvement in Adolescents' Learning and Academic Achievement: Cross-lagged Effect and Mediation of Academic Engagement. *Journal Youth Adolescence*, Vol. 50, 1811-1823.
- Zrilić, S., Marin, K. (2019). Kompetencije u suvremenoj školi – potrebe prakse iz perspektive učitelja. *Školski vjesnik: časopis za pedagoški teoriju i praksu*, Vol. 68, No.2, 389–400.